

The Impact of using BIM-based building performance analysis for housing projects in Iraq

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Abstract— The development of computer application for engineers and architects from the basic Computer Aided Drawing system (CAD) to Building Information Modeling system (BIM) not only allowed designers and architects to visualize buildings but also to analyze and estimate their performance in a virtual environment. This enabled designers to maximize building's efficiency, performance and reduce building's carbon footprint along the whole building lifecycle.

This research is looking at the potential impacts of using BPA and BIM technologies to achieve better building performance with special focus on the housing system in Iraq. The impact, nevertheless, applies to other types of buildings as well. The research will achieve its goal via the following objectives:

- What is BIM?
- How could BPA be applied through BIM? And the main differences compared to the traditional methods.
- What are the main advantages and disadvantages of using BIM for building performance?
- The Impact of using BIM for building performance analysis of affordable housing projects.

Index Terms— Building Information Modeling (BIM), Building Performance Analysis (BPA), Housing in Iraq, Environmental Impacts, Affordable Housing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advancements in environmental science lead to the realization of the huge impact of buildings on the environment. Housing is considered one of the most important types of buildings as it is directly associated with people's lives and any improvements could have huge effects on the environment in the long term [1]. Engineers and designers used to estimate environmental impact of buildings through conventional analysis tools that was based on specific mathematical expressions which was handled manually. The introduction of advanced computer-based system facilitated the analysis of buildings' design and helped estimating its environmental impacts. With the rising complexity of building's design and environmental requirements as well as the need for more accurate, fast and reliable analysis made the use of advance computerized systems such as CAD-based and BIM systems a necessity these days, especially when analyzing large developments such as mega redevelopment and housing projects.

This research is concerned with the impact of using Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Building Performance Analysis (BPA) on housing projects in Iraq. It will start by

defining BIM system and giving a brief background about its origins and development. Following that, the research will analyze BIM system process for analyzing building performance during building's lifecycle. While comparing BIM to the traditional methods usually used in Iraqi organization such as CAD-based systems. Then, the research will critically discuss the main advantages and disadvantages of implementing BIM system for handling building performance analysis. Following that, the research will highlight the potential benefits of using BIM for decreasing housing costs especially for affordable housing projects. Finally, the research will highlight some key points in the conclusions.

II. THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPUTER-BASED BUILDING DESIGN SYSTEMS

The revolution of computer systems during the last century meant the ability to handle complex mathematical calculation faster, easier and more reliable. Amongst many computer applications, Computer Aided Design (CAD) applications allowed engineers to draw 2D drawings of the building's design, its structure and the associated support systems. This made it much easier to do complex calculations of the building design [2]. Additionally, the 3D visualization of the building in a virtual environment provided a new mechanism to understand buildings construction. It allowed engineers to better estimate the area and volume of the building, handle light and sun analysis, estimate heating and cooling loads, and many other aspects which all helped towards understanding the environmental impact of a building [3, p. 3]. However, Computer Aided Design applications could not cover all of the different aspects of environmental analysis, also CAD based applications were never inclusive in terms of environmental analysis and the user was required to have a very deep understanding of the tools and the use of a number of applications to be able to analyze the building [4, p. 3]. In addition, most CAD-based applications did not have the options to include the physical information of the materials such as heat resistant (R-value), heat storage, weight and density, thus requiring the user to transfer the completed 3D Visualization of the building to another application and enter the physical data to be able to analyze its environmental impacts.

Building Information Modeling (BIM) was first introduced in the 1970s [2, 5], nevertheless, it was first implemented in Graphisoft's ArchiCAD in 1987 under the name "Virtual Building" [6, 7]. The term "BIM" became popular after

Autodesk's published a report explaining the system [8] as well as several web articles explaining why BIM should be the industry term for the system [9].

III. WHAT IS BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING (BIM)

BIM has gone through many improvements and developments since it was first introduced, thus its definition has gone through some changes and researchers have different definitions. According to Hergunsel (3 p. 5) "BIM is a three dimensional digital representation of a building and its intrinsic characteristics". The National BIM Standards in the United States defines BIM as "a digital representation of physical and functional characteristics of a facility. A BIM is a shared knowledge resource for information about a facility forming a reliable basis for decisions during its life-cycle" (10 p. 1). Steel et al and others (11; 12) define BIM as "an independent network of policies, processes and technologies. Which together constitute a methodology to manage the essential building design and project data in digital format throughout the buildings' lifecycle". Although these definitions differ in some aspects, they all define BIM as a system with virtual environment for modeling the building. They all consider that system a building specific running alongside building's lifecycle from planning to operation. Finally, they all focus on Information as being the new added dimension that allows engineers to further evaluate building's construction, processes and operation within the virtual environment. Autodesk defines BIM as "an intelligent model-based process that provides insight to help you plan, design, construct, and manage buildings and infrastructure" (13). This definition directly highlight the four stages of buildings' lifecycle covered by BIM that are Planning, Design, Construction and Operation. Although some researchers have different division of BIM workflow phases. They are, in most cases, just including sub-division to the general division and stages of BIM workflow (14), Hergunsel and many other researchers agree with this division of stages although they might differ in naming these stages (3 p. 9; 15) see Figure 1.

Figure 1: BIM project's lifecycle by Hergunsel [3, p. 9]

Since this research is concerned with the Building Performance Analysis in BIM and to the complexity and variety of subdivisions of these stages, the research will only discuss the general division and stages here but will go in further depth later on in the research when needed.

- According to Hergunsel (3), in the "Conceptual Design stage" and "Planning stage", the lead designer or architect and his/her team review the proposed project and the required resources and skills. They also start the legal contracts and understand them to ensure the deliverables they put for the project could be met. Additionally, the architect and the team build a simple representation for the design of the building to do some rough analyses.
- The "Design and Engineering stage" is where the team of engineers and architects design the building in full, ending with the full set of work-drawings and schedules such as quantities/specifications schedule. By the end of this stage, the building documentation provide full information about the project specification and design and the team have tackled most of the problems and issues in the design. This phase also include different analyses to justify and test the design of the building to the minor level possible and eliminate conflict (16).
- During the "Procurement and Construction stage" the procurement of the different resources including mechanical, human and materials starts. The delivery of these resources to the building site and initiation of the construction phase indicates the start for turning the design from the virtual environment to reality (2).
- The "Operation and Maintenance stage" is where a building start to perform its roles and objectives. The users start using the building, the different supportive systems start performing. BIM is beneficial in this phase through the ability to help in managing the building's users, users' needs, and systems more efficiently and effectively (3).

It could be argued here that a fifth stage could be added. This stage is associated with the end of building's lifecycle, BIM could help in the decision for the appropriate demolish approach, quantities and type of materials to result from demolish. Moreover, estimating the impact of removing the building on its surrounding buildings and area.

IV. THE APPLICATION OF BUILDING PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS (BPA) THROUGH BIM

According to Schlueter and Thesseling buildings in the United States alone account for almost 40% of energy consumption in the US, also buildings' energy consumption around the world accounts for about 40% of global CO2 emissions (17). The rising demand on energy and the growing awareness of the effects of CO2 emissions, as well as, the raising awareness of designers/engineers responsibility for minimizing the environmental impact of buildings. All that have pushed designers/architects and engineers to design more environmentally sensitive buildings to decrease its environmental impact (18).

Governments and professional organizations started putting building design criteria/codes and required planners, architects and engineers to apply them in their designs in order to minimize the environmental impacts of these designs. Such governments are the United States (19) and the United Kingdom (14). With the rising demand on building designs

that comply with environmental impacts codes, architects planners and engineers required a method to estimate buildings' environmental impact and try to minimize it through changes in design, material, and systems. Building Information Modeling provided the best environment to analyze building performance and make design changes virtually for the building (18). According to Autodesk, Building Performance Analysis (BPA) is "the process that uses BIM to driving a more efficient overall design through iteratively test, analyze, and improve building's design" (20). Although it should be highlighted here that all results are approximations of reality and hugely dependent on the accuracy of the building model used in the analysis and the knowledge of the user who interpret them. Building performance analysis deals with several aspects that all relate to building design. Kriegel and Nies (21) highlighted several aspects taken into consideration in BPA; first is the selection of Building Orientation that results in the minimum energy consumption possible. Second is analyzing Building Massing to optimize building envelope performance. Third is Daylighting Analysis that have impact on lighting and HVAC system. Fourth is Water Harvesting which could help reducing water needs. Fifth is Energy Modeling which could help in the reduction of energy requirements and analyze renewable energy systems such as windmills and solar panels. The sixth and final aspect is the use of Sustainable Materials by reducing materials needs and the usage of recycled materials.

Because all of above in addition to the fact that BIM links all buildings components with their physical properties, BIM is by far the best option to apply building performance analysis. According to Azhar et al. BIM is the perfect environment for building design analysis as all buildings components are five dimensional. Meaning that building objects and components in the representation do not have height, width and length properties only, additionally they are part of specific schedule of construction (time) and have physical properties such as heat resistant important for handling building performance analysis (16).

The default methodology/workflow for BIM and BPA design team as explained by Autodesk is as follows; first, the architect builds the basic geometry of the building in one of BIM virtual environment applications. Then another architect or engineer creates the energy model for the building geometry (Energy Analytical Model EAM). MEP engineer/s will create a design model for the piping, HVAC and electrical systems. Following that, the entire design team will start improving the design of building using building performance analysis of the now detailed building representation (20; 3).

Based on that it is possible to conclude that Building Performance Analysis could be applied in two stages:

A. The first is through the "Conceptual Planning/Design stage", in which simple representation of the building with low level of details is analyzed to estimate its environmental impact and make big changes to the building design in early stages before adding other details. The application of building performance analysis in this stage could dramatically decrease the time required for making big

changes to the design such as building orientation, shading and construction materials which otherwise might require a lot of time in later stages of building the virtual model in BIM as it directly affect supporting systems design (22).

B. The second stage is "Design and Engineering stage", in which fully detailed representation of the building is analyzed with all its supporting systems including HVAC, electrical and plumbing systems. This stage provides fully detailed analysis of the virtual model and the supporting system, thus allowing making changes to the minor levels. This could dramatically affect building performance in reality especially if changes are made to the heating and cooling systems, lighting of different spaces, design of windows and doors and other aspects of design (7).

It could be argued here that Building Performance Analysis could have direct impacts during other stages as well. For instance, in the "Procurement and Construction stage", BPA could help architects/contractors decide the building materials and components to use and their suppliers/fabricators, as it will raise their awareness to direct environmental impacts of the construction processes of the building. As for the "Operation and Maintenance stage", BPA estimations of space use and energy consumption could help better manage the building during operation, for example benefiting from the cool night to lower space temperature in advance before having heat-generating activity in the afternoon that follows for a specific hot day in the year. Another example is making sure future expansions and systems does not have bad influence on the overall building performance.

V. THE ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF BIM-BASED BUILDING PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Based on what was discussed earlier it is possible to conclude that BIM is a much better environment than CAD and other traditional systems when it comes to Building Performance Analysis (BPA). *Ajila* [10] concludes that traditional systems have deficiencies as they are associated with simplified assumptions made by the designer and engineers that is, in most cases, based on rules-of-thumb thus the results could be widely misleading and inaccurate. Additionally, traditional methods may force some aesthetic features that could have large impact on the building performance hence the environment. Lastly, traditional methods does not provide, in any term, an effective and efficient approach for measuring building design options performance thus making objective judgments and comparisons is not possible.

The building performance analysis with BIM can more accurately estimate the impact of design options as it is based on calculations of actual quantifiable data rather than rule-of-thumb assumptions. Furthermore, as BIM uses detailed building models in simulations, it could better analyze and represent the behavior of the building and its supporting systems. Finally, BIM-based building performance analysis provides a method for measuring the performance of the different alternatives and design options for the building as it is based on systems such as Level of Development (LOD) with LEED system, thus allowing comparison that is more objective and accurate [10, 11]. See figure 2.

Figure 2: Level of Development and BIM project phase source: [12]

It could be argued here that although BIM-based building performance analysis has many advantages over traditional methods, it requires all engineers to have good understanding of the tools required for analysis to produce accurate and complete results. Otherwise, the analysis could end with misleading results that could affect the building performance hugely. Furthermore, although building performance covers the analysis of building design and operation that is responsible for the most environmental impact as many researchers say [13, 14]. It still misses building impacts during the fabrication and production of building elements, transportation of resources, construction of the building and other aspects, which still accounts for a respectable amount of building impacts on the environment. Finally, the implementation of building performance analysis may require some changes in national laws, institutional structures, design teams, contracts and other related factors to successfully implement this system in the building design, construction and operation which could require a lot of time and effort especially for countries that did not experience such laws like Iraq. As an example, while design team members structure and relation in both CAD and BIM-based systems are very similar as they both include architects, civil and structural engineers, systems engineers (Mechanical, Electrical and Plumbing/Piping) as well as other member and engineers, the relation and responsibilities' allocation between teams may differ [15]. In the traditional CAD system -widely used in Iraq- team members work consequently meaning that architects will produce their plans then give them to the civil and structural engineers to design the structural system, and then MEP engineers will consequently design the supporting systems of the building. The traditional workflow involves a lot of going back and forth and the engineers have worked their way around it for years. In BIM, design team members start consequently but could work in parallel thus saving a lot of time and effort while improving the results and minimizing overlap work and collision in design [8, 15]; however, this change requires major changes in the structure of institutions, laws and standards especially when including Building Performance Analysis in the equation.

VI. BIM-BASED BUILDING PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS AND AFFORDABLE HOUSING IN IRAQ

Housing is the first type of buildings made by humans. Providing shelter against the different environmental factors as well as providing safety are some reasons to why this type of buildings are essential for human lives. Up to these days, housing form the majority of buildings built around the world not only in number but also in their land usage, resources and time requirements, thus they have huge impact on the environment beside their other impacts (27). Due to the rapid population growth, urbanization, migration, rising health needs, and modernization, the requirements of housing units dramatically increased in terms of the number and the standards of housing units (28; 29). Governments around the world started taking important role in the provision of housing units especially for low-income workers, as they are the most effected and incapable for producing housing units with good standards. This especially after the industrial revolution in Europe where large numbers of workers were brought to work in factories in industrial cities (29). In developing countries like Iraq, this notion was transferred over after the end of colonization era. This is because of modernization notions transferred from developed countries that caused developing countries to have similar problems (29; 30). In addition, religious and social factors promoted this notion as a way of providing justice and equity (31; 32).

Although Iraq has one of the first housing systems in the area (33). Presently, the country suffers from one of the most severe housing crisis (1). This could be attributed to a number of reasons such as political instability, wars, economic blockade, administrative corruption, absence of private sector affordable housing, Ill-considered laws and legislations, security crisis and many more factors (34). In 2003, the Iraqi Ministry for Construction and Housing estimated that Iraq need about 2.5 million housing units by 2016. The ministry put a strategic plan to fulfill that need via mega and big housing projects (35).

Just like in most counties, the rising demand on housing with higher standards and the outbreak of economic, environmental, social, planning, health and security problems in housing areas (36). All that required Iraqi government like many governments to put down a set of standards for housing planning and construction to guarantee the new housing units meet these standards (37; 38). However, as seen in other countries, the main problem facing the housing system particularly these days are derived not from putting these standards; rather it is associated with the implementation of these standards and making sure they are met in housing units. In short, governmental organizations associated with housing, need a method for; first, analyzing the housing units and check if they meet the standards, second monitoring and controlling the housing units to guarantee that they keep meeting these standards in the long term. Although, BPA in BIM cannot fully tackle the second problem in the environmental context, it can be extremely beneficial in addressing the first problem. There are a number of potential advantages from implementing BPA in housing projects especially for

affordable housing. This includes:

- More sustainable buildings/housing as BPA allow engineers to analyze housing buildings' design then making changes/choices for the design to be more sustainable such as decreasing power consumption, lowering waste producing and CO2 emissions. BPA could also raise awareness of the building design impact on the environment between engineers and people. This could help to improve the sustainability of other buildings' types in the future thus lowering the environmental impacts of buildings and new developments.
- BIM-based BPA have the ability to analyze new materials in a virtual environment. This allows engineers to test the impact of using local materials, recycled materials, or other materials that are more sustainable in the design of the building or any part of it to maximize sustainability without the need to test them in actual construction from the beginning. This does not mean eliminating the need for physical testing in the actual environment; rather it allows engineers to do these tests and analysis easier and at lower cost especially in first stages.
- Reducing costs in the short term. BPA could help reducing the costs of housing in the short term in many ways. For example, BPA could help designers to estimate the actual performance of the building and its components. This could help them identify where specific amount or type of materials are not needed in the building design thus eliminating it or changing it to a lower-cost material. Thus reducing the overall cost of the housing unit in the short term. For instance, based on BPA for a building, designers could decide to eliminate the insulation material from one side of the building, as it does not make meaningful improvements for its cost. Furthermore, the implementation of BPA could reduce building support systems and infrastructure. For example decreasing the size of air-conditioning units due to the improvements in passive cooling systems for the building. An example for the benefits of BPA for infrastructure is that by deciding to use water-recycling systems, the infrastructure size could be reduced and/or be more sustainable.
- Making housing more affordable in the long term. By implementing BPA, better choices of the infrastructure, systems, and building design could be made. These choices does not only result in decreasing power and water consumption, but it could also help by producing some or all of the required water and electricity locally. This would result in a huge power and water savings in the long term thus lowering the running costs of the housing units overall. Additionally, having such choices usually means lower spending on maintenance of the infrastructure and local systems, as they get smaller and more efficient. All this could result dramatic decrease of housing units costs in the long term.
- There are other advantages of implementing BPA in the national housing system. This include, enabling universities and professional organizations and bodies to monitor and track buildings performance thus cities' planning and the

potential common issues facing it in the long term, thus helping future researchers, professionals and planners to find solutions for these issues or make improvements to the design of buildings and the planning of cities. Other advantages are derived from producing building that are more sustainable such as better health, better self-esteem and social awareness of the global and local environmental challenges.

All these potential advantages of implementing BPA in design could have major impact in Iraq if applied through the national housing system. This is particularly because the country's housing laws and standards are undergoing huge changes and improvement as stated in the National Housing Policy in Iraq by the Ministry of Construction and Housing (MOCH) and UN-Habitat in 2010 (35). Another reason why this change could result in rapid improvements is the large number of mega redevelopment and housing programs that could amplify the good impact of implementing BPA for housing systems by a huge amount. Such projects are the 10x10 project and Bismayah in Baghdad as well as many other similar projects in other Iraqi governorates (39; 35; 40). From all that it is possible to foresee the potential impact of implementing Building Performance Analysis in the national housing standards in Iraq. However, to achieve the best results from BPA implementation, few housing and building standards should be changed. Another limitation is the institutional structure which need to be refined to allow the successful implementation of building performance analysis. The final limitation is derived from not having enough experience and knowledge in this section which could cause misleading results.

VII. CONCLUSION

The research gave a brief background about the advancement of computer applications in design and the role of Building Information Modeling in satisfying many aspects in design. These aspects are derived from Building Information Modeling being a five-dimensional system specified for building design and analysis. In addition to the three dimensions in older systems, BIM also included time and physical properties of building's components in building design. This allowed engineers and architects to analyze the building different criteria in a virtual environment and make modifications to improve the design before constructing it. This is the main reason why Building Performance Analysis (BPA) is much more feasible through BIM and it is the reason why BPA could have more accurate results than traditional methods.

The implementation of Building Performance Analysis carries many benefits. Beside the big improvements in the sustainability context such as reducing CO2 emissions and lowering power and water consumption, BPA could result in major short and long term cost savings for the users and the government. In addition, BPA could make design analysis and researches more feasible as it could serve as a tool for measuring the performance of building and the potential benefits of specific improvements. Likewise, BPA could be

used as a tool to enable future planning and ensure buildings and cities have acceptable performance and environmental impacts. The implementation of BPA in the Housing System in Iraq especially affordable housing could magnify these benefits especially because Iraq is undergoing major improvements in its housing standards and laws. In addition, the housing crisis and the strategic plan made by the government to overcome this crisis through mega redevelopment and housing projects like the 10x10 and Bismayah project in Baghdad could facilitate the implementation of BPA and maximize its potential benefits. However, this implementation does not come without limitations; BPA implementation requires changes to some housing laws and standards. It also needs modifications to the organizational structure and development of staff and tech in these organizations to make it work. Keeping all that in mind, BPA implementation in the Housing System in Iraq could still make huge changes for present and future generations faster and easier than in many countries and should be considered further by the different governmental and non-governmental organizations and researchers.

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